

1 **AUTOMATED CHROMATOGRAPHIC METHOD WITH FLUORESCENT**
2 **DETECTION TO DETERMINE BIOGENIC AMINES AND AMINO ACIDS.**
3 **APPLICATION TO CRAFT BEER BREWING PROCESS**

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9
10 **Abstract:** The combined determination of biogenic amines and amino acids is a challenge for
11 food scientists. In this research, a new methodology for the automatic on-line precolumn derivatization
12 and determination of 8 biogenic amines and 9 precursor amino acids by **Ultra-High Performance Liquid**
13 **Chromatography** with fluorescent detection has been developed. The method derivatized the analytes
14 with *o*-phthaldialdehyde and achieved the separation of the 17 derivatives in less than 15 minutes,
15 obtaining good quality parameters (limits of detection varied between **7.00 and 210 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$** , and RSD
16 intraday ranged between 1.5 and 6.0 %). The optimization of the derivatization procedure has been
17 carried out employing an experimental design and the Surface Response Methodology. The method has
18 been validated and applied to wine and beer, obtaining good recuperation percentages (**72.3 – 138.4%**).
19 Also, samples collected during the fermentation of a craft beer, as well as a bottled sample of the same
20 batch, have been analyzed, to monitor the changes in the profile of biogenic amines and amino acids.

21
22 **Keywords:** biogenic amines, amino acids, automatization, UHPLC-FD, Response Surface Methodology,
23 fermented beverages

25 **1. Introduction**

26 Biogenic amines (BAs) are nitrogenous compounds that have an important role in the human
27 metabolism, as they are involved in different processes (i.e. neurotransmission, regulation of blood
28 pressure, synthesis of DNA, RNA and proteins, or regulation of body temperature). BAs naturally occur
29 in protein-rich foodstuffs as fish, meat, vegetables or fruits, by the enzymatic decarboxylation of amino
30 acids (AAs). Fermented products (dairy products, beer and wine) could also have high levels of BAs,
31 due to the action of microorganisms. Conversely, spoiled foods and products manufactured under poor
32 hygienic conditions display high concentrations of some BAs, especially histamine, tyramine, putrescine,
33 and cadaverine. Hence, these compounds are an excellent indicator of the food quality [1,2].

34 Although their importance in the metabolism, high levels of BAs may be harmful, so the human
35 body has mechanisms to cope with them. However, poisoning can occur when large amounts of BAs are
36 consumed or when the ability to metabolize them is diminished by individual problems, medication or
37 alcohol consumption [1–3]. Among the more important symptoms, it can be pointed migraine and
38 hypertensive crisis [3]. Histamine is the most dangerous one, as it can cause psychoactive, vasoactive,
39 cutaneous and gastrointestinal effects. Also, tyramine is another relevant BA that may increase blood
40 pressure and cardiac frequency, and phenylethylamine may act as a powerful migraine inductor [1]. On
41 the other hand, putrescine and cadaverine are not themselves toxic, but they can increase the toxicity of
42 histamine, tyramine and phenylethylamine, because they interfere in detoxification reactions.
43 Furthermore, these two BAs can also produce negative effects on sensory quality of foods, giving them
44 putrefaction or rotting flesh flavour, respectively [2].

45 For this reason, it is necessary to develop fast and reliable methods for the determination of BAs
46 in foods, to control their levels, try to reduce them and ensure compliance with legislation [1,4]. Thus,
47 histamine in fishery products, for example, should not exceed 200 mg kg^{-1} , or 400 mg kg^{-1} in the case of
48 products matured in brine [5]. In fermented beverages as wine, limits have not been drawn up, but several

49 countries (Switzerland, Austria, Germany, Holland, Belgium and France) have established their own
50 recommendations for the histamine content, that ranged between 2 and 10 mg L⁻¹ [2].

51 Due to AAs are the precursors of BAs, there is a particular interest for food scientists for their
52 common determination, to obtain information about nutritional and hygienic quality, as well as enable
53 the monitoring of manufacturing processes [6]. However, the simultaneous determination of AAs and
54 BAs is complicated, due to the variety of structures (Figure 1) and the absence of good spectroscopic or
55 fluorescent properties [4,6,7].

56 The determination of these analytes has been carried out employing different techniques, such as
57 liquid chromatography, capillary electrophoresis or gas chromatography [1,8]. These separative
58 techniques are coupled to different detectors as DAD [3,4,6,9–12], FD [7,13–17] or MS/MS [18–25],
59 being the latter the most sensitive and reproducible, but also the most expensive, so it is not as accessible
60 equipment as the other two detectors. Also, this type of detector is normally employed to determine AAs
61 and BAs in biological samples as urine or brain tissue, due to the low concentration of the analytes in
62 these types of samples.

63 Among these techniques, liquid chromatography is the preferred one. The use of Ultra-High
64 Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) improves elution times, as well as the sensitivity and
65 selectivity of the methods. It is considered UHPLC when columns with a particle size smaller than 2 µm
66 are used, that withstand pressures up to 600 bar [4,6].

67 Sentellas et al. in 2016 [1] and Papageorgiou et al. in 2018 [8] reviewed the developed methods for
68 the determination of BAs in food samples, finding several methods that employed UHPLC. Other three
69 methods have been found that determine BAs in foodstuffs using UHPLC between 2017 and 2019
70 [4,11,24]. A pre- or post-column derivatization is usually necessary (employing dansyl chloride, *o*-
71 phthalaldehyde or 6-aminoquinolyl-*N*-hydroxysuccinimidyl carbamate as derivatization reagents).
72 Reverse phase is the usual mode employed, and mobile phases are formed by a mixture of acidic water

73 or buffer (ammonium formate/acetate or sodium acetate) and an organic solvent (ACN or MeOH,
74 sometimes acidified). Time of analysis ranged between 5 and 25 minutes, and mass, visible, ultraviolet
75 and fluorescent detection have been employed. The developed methods have been applied to very
76 different matrices, for example, fermented food (wine, cheese, soy sauce or beer), anchovy, seafood and
77 tuna. On the other hand, some methods have been found that determine amines with electrochemical
78 detection, but the analytes are amines with neurotransmitter functions, and that are found in brain dialysis
79 samples [26–30].

80 The determination of AAs by UHPLC usually has been focused on biological samples (serum,
81 urine, blood...) and their importance as biomarkers of different diseases such as schizophrenia, or
82 Alzheimer's disease [18,25]. There are also methods that determine AAs in foods (black onion, fermented
83 foods and beverages, tea, etc.), usually in conjunction with other analytes (biogenic amines, ammonium
84 ions, phenolic compounds or total antioxidant activity) [3,4,6,12,19,31]. In these methods, AAs are
85 usually determined by pre-column derivatization with ultraviolet detection. Some derivatization
86 reactions take long times and it is not possible to couple them to the chromatographic system.

87 The on-line derivatization procedures offer several advantages over off-line ones, among which it
88 can be highlighted [7,32]:

- 89 • All derivatized products are injected into the system, so there are no problems of dilution of the
90 derivatized products, as it could happen on the off-line derivatization.
- 91 • Sample handling is minimized, as well as the associated errors.
- 92 • Automated derivatization procedures tend to provide better reproducibility than manual ones.
- 93 • In on-line pre-column derivatization, sample treatment (i.e. extraction or clean-up) is often also
94 integrated in the chromatographic process, and can be automatically performed.

95 On-line pre-column derivatization must satisfy some conditions, such as good stability and
96 compatibility of the derivatizing reagent with the mobile phase; no precipitation or gas generated during

97 the derivatization reaction; and good solubility of the derivatized products into the mobile phase. This
98 type of derivatization is achieved by the incorporation of the derivatizing reagent into the flow scheme
99 of the chromatographic system, either in the mobile phase or through the use of an automatic injector
100 [32].

101 To the best of our knowledge, there are no methods that use on-line derivatization to determine
102 BAs and AAs together, although some methods determining BAs or AAs separately, using on-line
103 reactions, have been published, for example, Hyötyläinen et al. (2001) [15]; Zacharis et al. (2006) [7]
104 and Peng et al. (2008) [16]. All these methods agree in using *o*-phthalaldehyde as a derivatizing agent,
105 because the reaction is immediate, to determine 9 BAs in wine of different countries, 14 AAs in
106 pharmaceutical products, or histamine in different foods, respectively.

107 In this research, a new on-line **automatic** pre-column derivatization reaction coupled to UHPLC
108 with fluorescence detection is presented for the simultaneous quantification of 8 BAs and 9 AAs.
109 Derivatization and chromatographic conditions have been optimized, employing experimental design
110 and the Response Surface Methodology for the reaction optimization. In these conditions, all the analytes
111 are determined in 15 minutes, obtaining good figures of merit. The method has been applied to wine and
112 beer samples.

113

114 **2. Materials and Methods**

115 **2.1. Chemicals**

116 Eight BAs and nine AAs were determined in this study: putrescine (PUT; Sigma), agmatine (AGM;
117 Alfa Aesar), cadaverine (CAD; Aldrich), ethanolamine (ETA; Merck), histamine (HIM; Sigma),
118 tyramine (TYM; Sigma), tryptamine (TRY; Aldrich), 2-phenylethylamine (PEA; Aldrich), glutamic acid
119 (GLU; Sigma), serine (SER; Sigma), histidine (HIS; Fluka), arginine (ARG; Sigma-Aldrich), glycine
120 (GLY; Panreac), tyrosine (TYR; Merck), lysine (LYS; Aldrich), tryptophan (TRP; Panreac), and
121 phenylalanine (PHE; Aldrich-Chemie). Octylamine (OCT; Fluka) was used as internal standard (IS).

122 BAs stock solutions of 5000 mg L⁻¹ (31 – 82 mM, according to the molecular weight of each analyte)
123 and AAs stock solutions of 10000 mg L⁻¹ (49 – 133 mM, according to the molecular weight of each
124 analyte) were prepared in diluted HCl (0.1 M; Panreac) and stored refrigerated at darkness. Working
125 analyte solutions were prepared daily by mixing all the analytes and diluting them in 0.1 M HCl to obtain
126 the appropriate concentrations needed.

127 Weekly, a boric acid/sodium borate buffer (pH 10.50; 0.6 M) was prepared using boric acid and
128 NaOH, purchased from Merck and Panreac, respectively. Then, derivatization reagent was prepared as
129 follows: 1.6 mL of a dilution of *o*-phthalaldehyde (OPA; 2.98 mM in MeOH; purchased from Aldrich
130 and Panreac, respectively) and 1.2 mL of 2-mercaptoethanol (2-ME; Sigma-Aldrich) were added to a 5.0
131 mL volumetric flask, which was filled up to the mark with the aforementioned boric acid/sodium borate
132 buffer. The derivatization reagent was filtered before its use employing 0.22 µm membrane nylon filters
133 (Teknokroma).

134 For the chromatographic separation, acetonitrile UHPLC-grade (Sigma-Aldrich), methanol
135 UHPLC-grade (Panreac), and a TRIS buffer were used as mobile phase. TRIS buffer was prepared by
136 dilution in ultrapure water of the adequate amounts of Trizma® base (2-amino-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-
137 propanediol; Sigma) and tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane hydrochloride (Acros) to obtain a
138 concentration of 0.10 M and a pH of 8.30. Before its use, mobile phase was filtered (0.22 µm membrane
139 nylon filter; Teknokroma), and ultrasonicated.

140 The wines and beer analysed were obtained from local markets and were kept refrigerated and in
141 darkness until their analysis. The beer samples collected during the craft beer brewing process were
142 donated by a beer brewery company (Extremadura, Spain), and frozen at -20°C until their analysis. Also,
143 a bottled beer of the same batch was obtained and analysed 5 months after the bottling.

144

145 ***2.2. Instrumentation and software***

146 **Experiments** were carried out in an Agilent Model 1260 Infinity High Performance Liquid
147 Chromatograph (Agilent Technologies) equipped with an online degasser, quaternary pump (G1311B),
148 column oven compartment (G1316A), autosampler (G1329B), UV-Vis diode-array detector (G1315D)
149 and fluorescence detector (G1321B). The ChemStation software was used to treat data and control the
150 instrument. For the separation of the derivatives a Zorbax Eclipse Plus-C18 analytical column (100 x 4.6
151 mm; 1.8 μm ; Agilent Technologies) was employed.

152 Calibration curves and analytical figures of merit were calculated using ACOC software
153 (programmed in MATLAB code) [33]. **Experimental design and Surface Response Methodology were**
154 **carried out employing The Unscrambler v9.7 (CAMO Software).**

155

156 **2.3. Online and automated *pre-column* derivatization reaction**

157 Derivatization reagent was prepared as aforementioned (section 2.1). Then, 0.4 mL of a mixture of
158 AAs and BAs standards solutions (**prepared from the mixture of the appropriate volumes of stock solution**
159 **of each analyte and its dilution in HCl, 0.1 M, to obtain** concentrations ranged between **0.40 – 49.0 μM**
160 **and 0.16 – 7.8 μM** , for AAs and BAs respectively, in the reaction mixture) and 0.4 mL of internal standard
161 (OCT; **0.039 mM**) were mixed and diluted to a total volume of 5.0 mL with HCl 0.1 M.

162 The derivatization reaction was fully automated by means of an injector programme, which mixed
163 the reagents by drawing them sequentially into the injection seat. Then, the mixture was injected into the
164 column to separate the derivatives. The steps of the automatic injection, **as well as the concentrations of**
165 **analytes, IS and derivatizing reagent in the final mixture**, are summarized in Table 1. The optimization
166 of the reaction parameters was performed by using the Surface Response Methodology.

167

168 **2.4. Calibration curve**

169 The calibration curves were established by means of the internal standard method. Standards were
170 prepared following the methodology explained in section 2.3. Once obtained the chromatograms under
171 the optimized conditions, they were processed using the ChemStation package.

172

173 **2.5. UHPLC-FD method**

174 The mobile phase employed was composed by a TRIS buffer (pH 8.30; 0.10 M) (eluent A), ACN
175 (eluent B) and MeOH (eluent C).

176 The elution of the derivatives was performed using a gradient mode, consisting in four linear steps
177 summarized in Table 2. The flow rate was fixed at 1.0 mL min⁻¹, and the column was thermostated at
178 50°C. The eluate was fluorimetrically monitored (356/445 nm), using the peak area/IS area ratio as
179 analytical signal.

180

181 **2.6. Analysis of real samples**

182 Wine and beer samples were sonicated and filtered (0.22 µm, nylon) before its analysis. Samples
183 were analysed by means of the standard addition method, combined with internal standard method. To
184 prepare the samples, 0.4 mL internal standard (OCT; 0.039 mM), 0.2 mL wine/beer (diluted when
185 necessary) and 0.2 mL of a mixture of AAs and BAs standard solutions were put into a 5.0 mL volumetric
186 flask, which was filled up to the mark with HCl 0.1 M.

187 Then, the procedures explained in sections 2.3. and 2.5. were followed. All the analyses were
188 carried out by triplicate (n = 3). Peak area/IS area ratio obtained measuring the fluorescence at 356/445
189 nm was used as analytical signal.

190 At the end of the working day, the column was cleaned by the injection of 100 µL of MeOH and
191 going through the column first ultrapure water for 40 minutes and then ACN:MeOH (50:50) for 40
192 minutes.

193

194 **3. Results and discussion**

195 ***3.1. Optimization of chromatographic conditions***

196 For the chromatographic separation of the analytes, a previously optimised chromatographic
197 method for the separation of BAs (unpublished data) was firstly used, in which the mobile phase
198 consisted of ACN and TRIS buffer, and the stationary phase was an Eclipse Plus C18 column (100 x 4.6
199 mm; 1.8 μm). As more analytes (the precursor AAs) were introduced, the derivatives overlapped, so this
200 method had to be modified. The concentration of the TRIS buffer was slightly increased from 0.08 to
201 0.10 M to improve its buffering capacity, maintaining its pH (8.30). Also, attempts were made to modify
202 flow and gradient, but it was found that it was necessary to modify the selectivity of the mobile phase to
203 separate some derivatives, so the flow was maintained at 1.0 mL min⁻¹ and a new solvent (MeOH) was
204 introduced.

205 At first, the percentages of the aqueous phase were maintained and the percentages of the organic
206 phase were modified, increasing the percentage of MeOH. Then, gradient steps were also modified, until
207 obtaining the gradient showed on Table 2. In these conditions, the chromatogram showed in Figure 2
208 was obtained, and it can be seen that all the analytes are determined in less than 15 minutes.

209

210 ***3.2. Optimization of the online and automated derivatization reaction***

211 The literature was reviewed [7,16,17] and some previous studies were performed to fix the initial
212 conditions of the derivatization reaction. With this in mind, the following characteristics were
213 established:

- 214 • Sandwich injection (derivatizing agent + sample + derivatizing agent).
- 215 • Fixed sample volume (5 μL). Sample was prepared with the corresponding standards/real
216 sample and the internal standard.

217 • Derivatizing reagent prepared from OPA, 2-ME and boric acid/sodium borate buffer.

218 Also, some tests were carried out to verify which type of injection (draw sequentially or into seat)
219 and which speed gave the best results, obtaining that the reaction reached a greater extension when the
220 reagents were drawn sequentially and all the steps were made at default speed (90 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$).

221 Once these previous studies were performed, it was decided to carry out an experimental design
222 for the others parameters optimization. A central composite design was employed, with three variables
223 and two replicas for each experiment (except the central point, which was performed four times),
224 obtaining a total of 32 experiments. The variables introduced in the experiment were mix times (between
225 0 and 60), volume of derivatizing reagent to be injected (between 0.5 and 8.0 μL) and waiting time before
226 injecting the mixture (between 0 and 5 minutes).

227 The optimum parameters were selected employing the Surface Response Methodology (SRM).
228 The SRM searches for the optimum value of the variables that result in the maximum value of the
229 response function that defines the system under study. The difficulty lies in designing the appropriate
230 response function. For this study, the chosen response function (Equation 1) relates positively the sum
231 of areas (parameter used for quantification) and the product of the peaks resolutions that appear the
232 closest in the chromatogram (zone from 6.0 to 7.5 minutes), and negatively the total time of analysis
233 (parameters used for peaks separation). A statistical ANOVA analysis gives the goodness of the response
234 surface obtained from this response function, through the adjustment coefficient (R^2), and the lack of fit,
235 whose statistic p greater than 0.05 indicates that the model fits well.

236 This function fixed 2.0 μL of derivatizing reagent as the optimum volume, and, by setting this
237 condition, two possible optimal conditions were obtained: A) 10 mix and 5 minutes of waiting time; or
238 B) 60 mix and 1 minute of waiting time, as it can be seen in Figure 3.

239
$$F = \frac{\sum A \cdot \pi R_s}{t}$$

240 **Equation 1.** *Response function employed for the obtention of the optimum parameters, where*
241 *“A” is area, “R_s” is the resolution between peaks and “t” is total time of analysis.*

242
243 Both possibilities were compared, obtaining very similar chromatograms, with equal signals and
244 the same total analysis time. The decision was made on the basis of the best separation between AGM
245 and CAD, which were better resolved with the second option.

246 Thus, the optimal parameters for automatic and on-line derivatization of the biogenic amines and
247 the amino acids were 2.0 μL of derivatizing reagent (4.0 μL in total, because it is injected in sandwich
248 mode), 60 mix and 1 minute of waiting before injection, as it can be seen in Table 1.

249 **3.3. Evaluation of the method performance**

250 Under the optimal experimental conditions, the linearity and detection and quantification limits
251 were studied, employing a mixture of BAs and AAs standards, which were injected in triplicate. The
252 precision was calculated inter- and intra-day, employing two different levels of analyte concentrations
253 (low and high).

254 The developed automated on-line derivatization reaction coupled to UHPLC-FD method
255 presented good linearities (98.48 – 99.45%) with determination coefficients (R^2) which ranged between
256 0.9970 and 0.9996. Precision was evaluated as relative standard deviations (RSD) of six and ten repeated
257 measurements, for inter- and intra-day, respectively. These values are reported in Table 3, together with
258 the detection limits (calculated by the Long and Winefordner method [34]) and the quantification limits
259 (calculated as 3.3 times the detection limit of Long and Winefordner). Detection limits (LOD) ranged
260 from 7.00 to 206 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, while quantification limits (LOQ) varied between 22.0 and 681 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.

261 In previous studies, a manual off-line pre-column method was established (data not published),
262 but it was only applied to the determination of biogenic amines. Even so, the quality parameters obtained
263 in both cases have been compared (Table S1 – Supplementary Material), finding that, in general, the
264 determination coefficient (R^2), the detection limits (obtained by the Long- Winefordner method) and the

265 analytical sensitivity have been improved by using the automatic on-line methodology. Furthermore, the
266 intraday relative standard deviation (RSD) has improved, thus improving the precision of the method.

267 In addition, it should be kept in mind that the automatic on-line method double the number of
268 analytes determined, and that the possibility of performing derivatization in the equipment allows for
269 increased working hours and facilitates the analysis of samples.

270

271 **3.4. Application of the method to real samples of wine and beer**

272 The proposed method was validated in beer and wine samples, employing a series of test samples
273 that were spiked with known concentrations of the analytes. For this purpose, in a topaz vial, aliquots of
274 solutions containing 200 μ L of sample (wine diluted 1:2 and beer without dilution), 200 μ L of addition
275 standard and 400 μ L of internal standard (OCT, 0.039 mM) and filled up to 5.0 mL with HCl 0.1 M; and
276 aliquots of derivatizing reagent prepared from 1.6 mL OPA (2.98 mM) and 1.2 mL 2-ME, filled up to
277 5.0 mL with boric acid/sodium borate buffer (pH 10.5; 0.6 M), were placed. The concentrations of the
278 analytes were then determined by the developed method, using standard addition method combined with
279 internal standard. In Table 4, average recoveries of a beer, a white wine and a red wine sample are shown,
280 which varied between 72.3 and 138.4%, showing a satisfactory agreement between the analytes
281 concentrations taken and found.

282 On the other hand, in order to know if matrix effect was present, the calibration curve equations
283 obtained by internal standard were compared with those obtained using standard addition method
284 (combined with internal standard). The slopes of the curves were significantly different, so standard
285 addition method (combined with internal standard) was chosen for the determination.

286 Found concentrations of the different analytes are shown on Table 4. As it can be seen, GLY,
287 TYR, PUT, ETA, TRP and TYM appear in all samples, although in quite variable concentrations; while
288 TRY and PEA do not appear. For blonde beer, the AAs in highest concentration are TYR and HIS, while

289 PUT is the main BA found. On the other hand, there are big differences between the two types of wine.
290 Red wine presents average concentrations of all compounds, with TYR and ETA being the main AA and
291 BA, respectively. Meanwhile, white wine has much higher concentrations of TYR and ARG. HIS and
292 TRP also appear in high concentrations and, with regard to BAs, they present lower concentrations than
293 red wine or beer. In all cases, the total AAs concentration ($74.0 - 505.2 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$) is much higher than that
294 found for BAs ($18.3 - 42.6 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$). The red wine is the one that presents less AAs, and the white wine
295 the one that presents more, having 3.5 times the concentration that presents the blonde beer. In the case
296 of the BAs, the red wine presents greater concentration, and the white wine is the sample that present
297 less.

298 ***3.5. Application of the method to beer samples collected during craft beer brewing process***

299 The main stages of the craft brewing process are: malting, grinding and maceration, cooking and
300 cooling, fermentation and bottling and maturation. During the fermentation, the yeast is added to the
301 cooked must in the fermentor, and the enzymes transform the sugars into alcohol and mark the profile of
302 the beer. This process occurs at a temperature of 20°C , and usually lasts between 7 and 10 days. During
303 this process, the must has to be protected from the presence of oxygen. Finally, during bottling and
304 maturation beer is kept for a while at a cool ($16 - 20^{\circ}\text{C}$) and dry place to stabilize the flavor and aromas
305 obtained.

306 Samples analysed during this research were donated by a craft brewery (Extremadura, Spain),
307 which prepares different types of beer. In this case, samples were from a blonde beer with type Ale
308 fermentation. Samples were collected during the 9 days that the fermentation of the beer lasted, and kept
309 frozen until their analysis. Also, a sample of the finished bottled beer was analysed. Samples were
310 filtered, sonicated and diluted, when necessary, before their analysis, which was carried out by means of
311 the standard addition method (combined to internal standard method), due to the existence of matrix
312 effect.

313 Table 5 shows the concentrations of AAs and BAs found during the fermentation and in the
314 bottled beer, and it can be noticed that the components profile varied over time. Regarding AAs, first day
315 it can be observed a must very rich in AAs, in which all AAs are present except for GLY, with a total
316 concentration of 390.0 mg L⁻¹, being TYR the main AA present (161 mg L⁻¹). The following days, total
317 concentration of AAs sharply decreased to 2.0 mg L⁻¹ in the fifth day. It is important to note that SER
318 disappeared the second day to form GLY, which appeared from that moment on. Other AAs (as GLU,
319 ARG, TYR, LYS, TRP and PHE) also decreased their concentration until not detected in some point.
320 After the fifth day, the concentrations of AAs increased over time. The AAs that increased their
321 concentrations were HIS, ARG, GLY, TYR, LYS and TRP, while GLU, SER and PHE remained
322 undetected. The total AAs concentration on the last day before bottling was 127.0 mg L⁻¹, approximately
323 one third of the initial concentration of the must, with TYR remaining the main AA present (62 mg L⁻¹).
324 In bottled beer, the AAs content increased by approximately 50% to 234.0 mg L⁻¹. Important changes
325 include the disappearance of ARG and the appearance of SER, as well as the sharp increase in the
326 concentration of HIS, TYR and TRP. GLY and LYS also increase their concentration, but much more
327 slightly.

328 On the other hand, concerning the BAs, only PUT, AGM and ETA appear, being the rest
329 undetected during all the fermentation process. Their total concentration in the first day must was of 15.6
330 mg L⁻¹, being much lower than that obtained for AAs (specifically, 25 times less). Their concentrations
331 suffer minor changes during time, but the fifth day their concentration reached its lowest valor (6.6 mg
332 L⁻¹), as in AAs concentration; however, it was the only time when BAs concentration was higher than
333 AAs concentration. The following days, total BAs concentration increased, reaching 20.7 mg L⁻¹ the day
334 before the bottling. The BA in higher concentration during all the fermentation process was the AGM,
335 which is the only BA that comes from the malt. Finally, in bottled beer, the content of BAs suffered a
336 great increase, reaching a concentration 4 times greater (81.0 mg L⁻¹). Only PUT, ETA and AGM
337 continued to appear, although TYM was detected (without being quantifiable). The main increase

338 corresponded to the concentration of AGM, which increased approximately 80% with respect to the last
339 day of fermentation. This increase may be influenced by the disappearance of ARG.

340 It could be observed that, although having precursors of all BAs, most of them do not appear,
341 which could mean that the microorganisms responsible for the decarboxylation of AAs would be not
342 present in the analysed must.

343

344 4. Conclusions

345 In this work, a new method for the automatic on-line **pre-column** derivatization of 8 biogenic
346 amines and 9 precursor amino acids has been optimized through experimental design and Surface
347 Response Methodology. The obtained derivatives were chromatographically separated by UHPLC with
348 fluorescent detection, using reverse phase and a simple mobile phase. Under these conditions, the 17
349 derivatives and the internal standard were separated in less than 15 minutes, obtaining a fast method with
350 good linearity and sensibility (determination coefficients between 0.9970 and 0.9996 and LODs between
351 **7.00 and 206 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$**), easy to implement in a quality laboratory.

352 The method has been validated and applied to three types of fermented beverages (blonde beer,
353 red wine and white wine), obtaining very different profiles of biogenic amines and amino acids. Some
354 compounds appear in all samples (GLY, TYR, PUT, ETA, TRP and TYM), while TRY and PEA are not
355 present in any of them. Samples collected during the fermentation process of a blonde Ale craft beer
356 were also analysed employing the developed method, obtaining a BAs and AAs profile that changed over
357 time, and in which, although a lot of precursor AAs were present in the must, only three BAs appeared
358 (being one of them AGM, which naturally occurs in the malt), so, apparently, the microorganisms
359 responsible for decarboxylation of AAs were not present in the must. This is an indication of the good
360 microbiological quality of the analysed must. In addition, it has also been found that the profile of AAs
361 and BAs varies during the maturation and bottling process, as the concentrations of AAs and BAs found
362 in a finished beer from the same batch indicate 2 times more AAs, as well as 4 times more BAs.

363 With regard to changes in the characteristics of craft beer from bottling to consumption, the
364 bibliography includes a study [35] on the loss of qualities referring to one of the components of hops,
365 recommending maintaining the beer at cool temperature and consumption before three months. In this
366 way, it could also be interesting to monitor changes in the concentrations of AAs and BAs from bottling
367 and throughout their useful life, using the proposed method.

368

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375

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497

498

499 **Figure captions**

500 **Figure 1.** Structure of the biogenic amines and precursor amino acids studied during this research. ARG:
501 arginine; AGM: agmatine; GLU: glutamic acid; PUT: putrescine; HIS: histidine; HIM: histamine; SER:
502 serine; ETA: ethanolamine; LYS: lysine; CAD: cadaverine; TRP: tryptophan; TRY: tryptamine; TYR:
503 tyrosine; TYM: tyramine; PHE: phenylalanine; PEA: 2-phenylethylamine.

504

505 **Figure 2.** Chromatogram of the derivatives of biogenic amines and precursor amino acids obtained under
506 optimal conditions, after on-line derivatization and chromatographic separation. For abbreviations, see
507 Figure 1.

508

509 **Figure 3.** Response surface obtained by using the response function (Equation 1), and setting the OPA
510 volume to 2.0 mL.

511

886.802

1.474e+03

2.061e+03

2.648e+03

3.235e+03

3.822e+03

RESULT1, Y-var:*, (X-var = value): OPA volume (B) = 2.00

Table 1. Injection programme for the on-line pre-column derivatization of the amino acids and the biogenic amines.

FUNCTION	VOLUME	SUBSTANCE	DETAILS
Draw	2 μL	Derivatization reagent	Default speed (90 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) Default offset
Wash needle		MeOH-H ₂ O	2 times
Draw	5 μL	Sample	Default speed (90 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) Default offset
Wash needle		MeOH-H ₂ O	2 times
Draw	2 μL	Derivatization reagent	Default speed (90 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) Default offset
Wash needle		MeOH-H ₂ O	2 times
Mix	Default volume (9 μL)	Mixture	From air Default speed (90 $\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) 60 times
Wait			1 minute
Inject	9 μL	Reaction mixture	[AAs]: 0.40 – 49 μM [BAs]: 0.16 – 7.8 μM [IS]: 1.7 μM [OPA]: 0.42 mM

Table 2. Elution gradient optimized for the separation of the amino acids and the biogenic amines derivatives.

TIME (min)	%A (TRIS buffer)	%B (ACN)	%C (MeOH)
0	80	6	14
6	50	17.5	32.5
14	0	35	65
15	80	6	14

Table 3. Method performance parameters. For abbreviations, see Figure 1.

	GLU	SER	HIS	ARG	GLY	TYR	LYS	PUT	AGM	CAD	ETA	TRP	HIM	PHE	TYM	TRY	PEA
t_R (min)	1.91	3.64	3.73	4.44	4.53	5.59	6.04	6.25	6.75	7.02	7.24	7.67	8.02	8.30	10.33	11.64	12.05
Linear range (mg L⁻¹)	0.15 – 10.0	0.075 – 5.0	0.15 – 5.0	0.10 – 1.25	0.03 – 1.25	0.15 – 5.0	0.05 – 2.5	0.03 – 0.625	0.03 – 1.25	0.03 – 0.625	0.01 – 0.50	0.10 – 5.0	0.04 – 1.25	0.10 – 5.0	0.04 – 1.0	0.04 – 1.0	0.01 – 1.0
R²	0.9983	0.9988	0.9982	0.9980	0.9975	0.9994	0.9996	0.9992	0.9977	0.9981	0.9992	0.9970	0.9984	0.9978	0.9971	0.9996	0.9980
Linearity (%)	98.85	99.02	98.81	98.77	98.60	99.34	99.45	99.23	98.67	98.80	99.24	98.48	98.90	98.71	98.50	99.44	98.75
LOD Long-Winefordner (µg L⁻¹)	206.4	79.4	96.4	25.8	29.4	53.3	21.4	8.8	30.1	13.9	6.6	123.2	24.7	104.8	27.6	10.4	22.9
LOQ (3.3·LOD_{L-W}) (µg L⁻¹)	681.1	262.0	318.1	85.1	97.0	175.9	70.6	29.0	99.3	45.9	21.8	406.6	81.5	345.8	91.1	34.3	75.6
Analytical sensitivity (γ⁻¹) (µg L⁻¹)	156.4	68.3	82.1	19.3	22.9	45.4	18.6	6.7	22.2	10.5	5.4	105.6	18.2	89.9	19.9	7.5	16.9
RSD intraday (%) (low point)	4.28	3.61	6.03	3.50	4.42	4.59	4.72	3.15	5.59	2.70	4.30	4.28	4.59	4.61	4.83	3.40	4.41
RSD intraday (%) (high point)	2.39	2.38	2.86	4.43	2.04	2.93	2.21	1.73	3.49	3.26	2.55	2.49	1.33	1.92	1.50	1.70	1.55
RSD interday (%) (low point)	5.01	5.90	3.34	8.75	7.64	7.38	8.85	6.19	11.09	12.6	9.32	6.50	7.11	5.81	6.78	8.38	6.89
RSD interday (%) (high point)	3.94	5.51	4.10	9.26	5.75	5.73	6.60	4.08	5.05	3.55	6.57	5.32	6.97	6.89	5.85	9.07	8.19

Table 4. Biogenic amines and precursor amino acids concentrations found in different samples of fermented beverages (\pm SD; mg L⁻¹). For abbreviations, see Figure 1.

	GLU	SER	HIS	ARG	GLY	TYR	LYS	PUT	AGM	CAD	ETA	TRP	HIM	PHE	TYM	TRY	PEA	TOTAL AAs	TOTAL BAs
BLONDE BEER	<0.15	<0.08	33 ± 6	n.d.	15 ± 1	73 ± 9	n.d.	18 ± 2	n.d.	n.d.	7.3 ± 0.9	13 ± 5	6.5 ± 0.8	11 ± 1	4 ± 1	n.d.	n.d.	145.2	35.8
RED WINE	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	10 ± 1	35 ± 9	11 ± 3	16 ± 1	<0.06	<0.03	20 ± 2	18 ± 5	3 ± 1	n.d.	3.5 ± 0.7	n.d.	n.d.	74.0	42.6
WHITE WINE	<0.15	n.d.	47 ± 16	56 ± 10	19 ± 2	320 ± 71	27 ± 3	8 ± 1	n.d.	n.d.	7.3 ± 0.9	27 ± 9	n.d.	9 ± 6	3 ± 1	n.d.	n.d.	505.2	18.3
Recuperation in beer (%)	97.3	97.7	88.5	98.9	91.8	78.7	103.2	107.4	92.8	88.9	111.0	93.8	108.5	99.4	121.9	104.1	102.5	94.0	104.6
Recuperation in red wine (%) *					99.7	117.3	101.7	120.7	96.8	72.3	138.4	88.5	110.7		94.7			101.8	105.6
Recuperation in white wine (%) *	81.3		75.3	82.2	101.8		110.1	129.9			107.8	85.7		94.3	93.2			105.1	110.3

*In wine samples appear the recuperations of the found analytes.

Table 5. Biogenic amines and precursor amino acids concentrations found in craft beer samples collected during elaboration process (\pm SD; mg L⁻¹). For abbreviations, see Figure 1.

	GLU	SER	HIS	ARG	GLY	TYR	LYS	PUT	AGM	CAD	ETA	TRP	HIM	PHE	TYM	TRY	PEA	TOTAL AAs	TOTAL BAs
DAY 1	39 \pm 8	18 \pm 3	40 \pm 4	42 \pm 6	n.d.	161 \pm 13	32 \pm 2	2.3 \pm 0.4	8 \pm 2	n.d.	2.3 \pm 0.3	29 \pm 4	n.d.	29 \pm 4	3 \pm 1	n.d.	n.d.	390.0	15.6
DAY 2	13 \pm 7	n.d.	13 \pm 4	9 \pm 2	7.2 \pm 0.6	131 \pm 15	3 \pm 1	2.4 \pm 0.2	8 \pm 1	n.d.	2.8 \pm 0.2	12 \pm 3	n.d.	7 \pm 3	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	195.2	13.2
DAY 3	8 \pm 4	n.d.	8 \pm 2	n.d.	3.8 \pm 0.7	16 \pm 3	2 \pm 1	2.1 \pm 0.3	7.0 \pm 0.9	n.d.	2.2 \pm 0.4	6 \pm 2	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	44.2	11.3
DAY 4	n.d.	n.d.	9 \pm 4	n.d.	4 \pm 1	22 \pm 10	2.6 \pm 0.9	3.2 \pm 0.8	11 \pm 2	n.d.	3.4 \pm 0.8	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	37.6	17.6
DAY 5	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	2.0 \pm 0.7	n.d.	n.d.	1.3 \pm 0.4	4 \pm 1	n.d.	1.3 \pm 0.6	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	2.0	6.6
DAY 6	n.d.	n.d.	14 \pm 5	n.d.	7 \pm 2	30 \pm 10	3 \pm 1	3.8 \pm 0.6	12 \pm 2	n.d.	4 \pm 1	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	54.0	19.8
DAY 7	n.d.	n.d.	15 \pm 5	n.d.	7 \pm 2	20 \pm 5	3 \pm 1	3.0 \pm 0.4	10 \pm 2	n.d.	3.0 \pm 0.6	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	45.0	16.0
DAY 9	n.d.	n.d.	31 \pm 5	6 \pm 1	10 \pm 1	62 \pm 8	7 \pm 1	3.8 \pm 0.3	12 \pm 1	n.d.	4.9 \pm 0.4	11 \pm 5	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	127.0	20.7
BOTTLED BEER	n.d.	14 \pm 5	74 \pm 18	n.d.	16 \pm 6	95 \pm 14	10 \pm 5	8 \pm 2	66 \pm 16	n.d.	7 \pm 2	25 \pm 12	n.d.	<LOQ	<LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	234.0	81.0

Table S1. Comparison of analytical parameters obtained using the manual off-line method (first row) and the automatic on-line one (second row).

	PUT	AGM	CAD	ETA	HIM	TYM	TRY	PEA
R²	0.9992	0.9917	0.9980	0.9992	0.9984	0.9971	0.9996	0.9980
	0.9961	0.9990	0.9965	0.9942	0.9988	0.9995	0.9981	0.9991
LOD (µg L⁻¹)	8.8	30.1	13.9	6.6	24.7	27.6	10.4	22.9
	22.4	16.3	21.4	10.8	17.6	5.6	11.6	6.3
Analytical sensitivity (γ⁻¹) (µg L⁻¹)	6.7	22.2	10.5	5.4	18.2	19.9	7.5	16.9
	16.8	11.7	16.1	8.4	12.6	3.7	7.7	5.2
RSD intraday (%) (low point)	3.15	5.59	2.70	4.30	4.59	4.83	3.40	4.41
	5.24	2.70	4.57	4.24	3.20	4.22	4.40	6.05
RSD intraday (%) (high point)	1.73	3.49	3.26	2.55	1.33	1.50	1.70	1.55
	2.37	1.62	1.44	1.45	1.58	1.90	1.49	1.69